

Global Interdisciplinary Research

The Influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Gross NPF (Non Performing Financing), and Mudharabah Income on GWM (Minimum Reserve Requirement) with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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ABSTRACT

By taking business size as a moderating variable, this research examines the influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Gross NPF, and Mudharabah Income on GWM. This research involved Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah in 2018.Q1 and Q3 2023. The sampling method was taken from the Research Library, and then processed using Microsoft Excel with 115 observations. Moderated regression analysis (MRA) and Panel Data Analysis were used, all using Eviews 12. The results showed that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds did not affect the GWM; the mudharabah income variable also does not affect the GWM; and the Gross NPF variable also does not affect GWM. It is shown that GWM is influenced simultaneously by the variables ZISWAF fund receipts, Gross NPF and Mudharabah Income.

KEYWORDS: ZISWAF, Gross NPF, Mudharabah income, GWM, Firm size

INTRODUCTION

Sharia Bank is a financial institution founded on sharia principles, guided by the Hadith of the Prophet. to create products and operations. In other words, this bank's main focus is to provide financing and other services that are in line with Islamic principles. Financial institutions have developed rapidly, dynamically and competitively in recent years (Kornitasari et al., 2023) .

Mudharabah income obtained from fund owners and managers, where mudharabah income is distributed to both parties after being agreed in a mudharabah contract, has the potential to increase bank profitability but also increases the risk of non-performing finance (NPF). High operational costs can affect mudharabah income margins, thereby reducing NPF gross income (Sumiyati, 2020) .

The main focus of Islamic banks is to provide business funds and other services using a repayment system and the distribution of money is carried out in line with the principles of Islamic law. Sharia banking initially operated without an interest system, but shared profits with customers. In the context of moderation in business size, mudharabah income can have an impact on monetary stability, bank management and business activities (Aji, 2022) .

Financial ratios such as the financing to deposit ratio (LDR) and ROA, which play a role in modernizing company benchmarks, can be influenced by mudharabah income. In addition, mudharabah income can be used as a source of funds for current account transactions to fulfill Mandatory Minimum Reserve obligations, as well as to fulfill tax

and other obligations. In addition, banking liquidity is influenced by mudharabah income; This has an impact on the Mandatory Minimum Reserve obligations and other regulations (Usman, 2000) .

Ziswaf is an Islamic social finance tool that allows the rich to help the poor. Apart from having a financial perspective, ZISWAF is also a form of worship that is both rewarding and obligatory. However, no Islamic country has yet made it the main instrument of fiscal policy. ZISWAF consists of zakat (obligation), infaq, alms, and waqf (sunnah), and is usually managed by one institution with various mechanisms in accordance with Islamic law (Latifah & Lubis, 2020) .

The performance of sharia financial institutions can be measured by looking at non-performing financing (NPF). In conventional financial institutions, this risk is called Non-Performing Loans or non-functioning credit, while in sharia financial institutions it is called NPF. The higher the ratio, the greater the risk of problematic funding that the bank will encounter (Kuswahariani et al., 2020)

Mudharabah income comes from collaborative efforts between two parties, namely the fund owner and the capital owner. In this partnership, the fund owner supports the capital owner in investing and sharing profits. Income generated from mudharabah is divided according to the agreement in the contract, where each party shares the risks and profits. (Zaenudin, 2015) .

GWM is the minimum amount of savings funds that financial institutions at Bank Indonesia must maintain as a checking account balance. In accordance with Indonesian Bank regulations, Bank Indonesia determines GWM as a special percentage of third party financing. Because the policy influences money market conditions, the GWM functions as an indirect monetary policy instrument with the aim of controlling the total funds distributed in society, therefore the percentage must be adjusted to the national economic situation. Bank Indonesia has made many changes in determining the GWM percentage required to be met by banks in Indonesia since it was implemented at the beginning of independence. The aim is to maintain the stability and stability of Indonesian banking liquidity during the crisis (Pradhana, 2016) .

The amount of assets owned by a company that are used for daily operations is known as company size. Large companies usually have many advantages over small companies because they have greater bargaining power, economies of scale, and greater specialization. So, large companies usually produce more than small businesses (Jonsson, 2007) .

Mudharabah income has the potential to influence monetary stability, bank management, and business activities in the context of moderating company size. Mudharabah income can act as a source of funds to carry out current account transactions required to fulfill Minimum Statutory Reserve obligations, and also as a source of funds to fulfill tax responsibilities and other aspects. Additionally, mudharabah income can have an impact on financial ratios, such as the financing to deposit ratio and return on assets (ROA), which in turn can influence how the business is sized. Mudharabah income can also influence banking liquidity conditions, which is an important factor influencing Statutory Reserve obligations and other regulations (Ross et al., 2021) .

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research aims to evaluate the impact of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Gross NPF, and Mudharabah Income on GWM, with Firm Size as a

moderating variable, during the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. It is hoped that this research will clarify how receiving funds from these sources affects the GWM, as well as how company size moderates the influence of receiving these funds.

This research uses a Panel Data Regression Model and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Interaction tests use an analytical approach that maintains sample integrity and provides a basis for assessing the influence of moderator variables (Ghozali, 2018) . model for the following panel data regression analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4Z + \beta_5X_1*Z + \beta_6X_2*Z + \beta_7X_3*Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = GWM

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

Gross NPF Fund Receipts

X3 = Mudharabah income

Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Interaction of the influence of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with moderation of firm size

Gross NPF fund receipts with firm size moderation

X3*Z = Interaction of the influence of Mudharabah income with the moderation of IRM size

e_i = Error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	3.581652	28386.30	5.261391	16.65104
Median	18,00000	3.230000	16366.00	5.090000	16.51000
Maximum	669879.0	11.28000	221513.0	11.90000	19.58000
Minimum	0.000000	0.670000	0.000000	0.000000	14.12000
Std. Dev.	87500.44	2.001544	37220.81	1.938077	1.474160
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

The total sample of financial industry research registered on the IDX from 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3 is 115 samples. The variable ZISWAF Fund Receipts (X1) has an average value of 25082.01, a median of 18.00000, a maximum value of 669879.0, and a minimum value of 0.00000, according to Table 1 showing the results of descriptive statistics.

Based on the descriptive statistical findings above, the wadiah current account savings variable (X2) has the following numbers: an average of 3.581652, a median of 3.230000, a maximum of 11.28000, a minimum of 0.670000 and a standard deviation of 2.001544.

According to the descriptive statistics results shown in Table 1, the Mudharabah Income variable (X3) has an average value of 28386.30, a median of 16366.00, a maximum value of 221513.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 37220.81.

According to the descriptive statistics results shown in Table 1, the company size

variable (Z) gets an average value of 16.65104, a median of 16.51000, a maximum value of 19.58000, a minimum value of 14.12000, and a standard deviation of 1.474160.

The Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM) variable (Y) has an average value of 5.261391, a median of 5.090000, a maximum value of 11.90000, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 1.938077. This is the descriptive statistical result of the GWM variable calculated using the Tobins'Q formula.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

The first analysis stage is to decide on a panel data regression model to determine the most suitable Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect.

Test Chow

This test was tried to determine which method is most suitable between (CEM) and (FEM).

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Prob.
Chi-square cross-section	0.1199

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Proving that the probability value of 0.1199 is actually as high as 0.05, as shown in table 2. Therefore, CEM is the most suitable for use in this test.

Lagrange Multiplier Test

This test is to select the best Common Effect Model and Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 3. LM Test Results

	Cross-section
Breusch-Pagan	0.452528 (0.5011)

From table 3 it can be concluded that the CEM model is suitable for this test because it proves that the Breusch-Pagan value of 0.5011 is higher than 0.05.

CLASSIC ASSUMPTION TEST

Normality Test

This test ensures that the error value of the regression equation is normally distributed. If the error value mostly matches the average value, the value is considered to be normally distributed. The method raised by Jarque-Bera has the following hypothesis to determine the residual normality test: H0: ϵ_i equals 0, error data is normally distributed; H1: ϵ_i is not equal to 0, error data is not distributed in a standard way.

Table 4. Normality Test Results

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

It was concluded that the data from this study was normally distributed. The Jarque test probability value is 0.004431, higher than 0.05.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test was carried out to determine whether the regression model found a relationship or not. If there is a correlation between two independent variables, their correlation value is not equal to zero and is called orthogonal.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1,000000	-0.117000	0.563171
X2	-0.117000	1,000000	-0.002403
X3	0.563171	-0.002403	1,000000
Z	0.519558	-0.169161	0.687612

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

Proving that the relationship to the independent variable must have a value above 0.85. These results conclude that there is no multicollinearity in the research data.

Heteroscedasticity Test

When the model error does not show constant variation throughout the observations, this is called heteroscedasticity. The white test is carried out by regressing the squared error values for all independent variables.

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	0.089637	0.054379	1.648375	0.1021
X1	1.13E-07	4.81E-08	2.359195	0.0201
X2	0.001324	0.001741	0.760697	0.4485
X3	-2.51E-09	1.35E-07	-0.018665	0.9851

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

Apart from the variable x1, there is no heterogeneity in the regression model in this research, as shown by the results of the heteroscedasticity test in table 6, which

shows that the resulting probability value is above 0.05.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

Demonstrates panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely CEM.

Table 7. Panel Data Regression Analysis

Variables	Coefficien		t-Statistics	Prob.
	t	Std. Error		
C	5.059208	2.772973	1.824471	0.0708
X1	1.13E-06	2.45E-06	0.459947	0.6465
X2	-0.328059	0.088763	-3.695879	0.0003
X3	-1.63E-06	6.86E-06	-0.238039	0.8123

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

Moderated Regression Analysis

Variables that have the ability to strengthen or reduce the correlation of independent and dependent variables are known as moderating variables. The test results of the analysis are shown here.

Table 8. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Variables	Coefficien		t-Statistics	Prob.
	t	Std. Error		
C	3.566271	5.067921	0.703695	0.4832
X1	-0.000475	0.000298	-1.594862	0.1137
X2	0.231043	1.137439	0.203126	0.8394
X3	0.000131	0.000101	1.292085	0.1991
X1Z	2.46E-05	1.53E-05	1.601459	0.1122
X2Z	-0.036261	0.071714	-0.505640	0.6141
X3Z	-6.94E-06	5.39E-06	-1.287100	0.2008

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

Statistical Test

T test

The T test is used to determine the independent variable as partially having a significant impact on the independent variable. In addition, the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable is evaluated at a significance level of 0.05, a confidence level of 95 percent, and an error size of 5 percent.

Table 9. T Test Results

Variables	Coefficien		t-Statistics	Prob.
	t	Std. Error		
C	3.566271	5.067921	0.703695	0.4832

X1	-0.000475	0.000298	-1.594862	0.1137
X2	0.231043	1.137439	0.203126	0.8394
X3	0.000131	0.000101	1.292085	0.1991
X1Z	2.46E-05	1.53E-05	1.601459	0.1122
X2Z	-0.036261	0.071714	-0.505640	0.6141
X3Z	-6.94E-06	5.39E-06	-1.287100	0.2008

Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

Hypothesis 1 (H1) shows that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an influence on GWM. With a probability figure of 0.1137, lower than the significant figure of 0.5 or 5%, this proves that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an influence on GWM in financial sector companies from 2018 Q1 to 2023 Q3.

Hypothesis 2 (H2) shows that gross NPF has no effect on GWM. With a probability figure of 0.8394, greater than the significant figure of 0.5 or 5%, this proves that gross NPF has no effect on GWM from 2018 Q1 to 2023 Q3.

Hypothesis 3 (H3) shows that mudharabah income influences GWM. With a probability figure of 0.1991, lower than the significant figure of 0.5 or 5%, this proves that mudharabah income influences the GWM in financial sector companies during the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3.

Hypothesis 4 (H4) shows that company size cannot moderate the effect of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on GWM in financial sector companies from 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3 because the probability number is 0.1122, which is lower than 0.5 or 5%.

Hypothesis 5 (H5) shows that company size cannot moderate the effect of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on GWM in financial sector companies from 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3 because the probability number is 0.6141, which is greater than 0.5 or 5%.

Hypothesis 6 (H6) shows that firm size cannot moderate the effect of murabahah income on GWM in financial sector companies from 2018. Q1 to 2023. Q3 because the probability figure of 0.2008 is increasingly lower than the significant figure of 0.5 or 5%.

F test

Coefficient of Determination, which proves how much the independent variable contributes to the regression model to prove variations in the dependent variable.

Table 10. F Test Results

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000019
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Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

In this research, it was carried out with a significant value of 0.05 or 5%, assuming that if the figure is less than 0.05, then the regression coefficient will be used. The numbers shown prove that the result of the significant number F is 0.000019, which is the result of the number being lower than the value of 0.05. So, it can be said that GWM is influenced by ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income simultaneously.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Showing many independent variables contributes to the regression model in explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 11. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Adjusted R-squared	0.225600
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Source: Eview s 12 (Data processed by the author)

These results for GWM on the dependent variable are shown in table 12, which shows an adjusted R² value of 0.225600. This shows that ZISWAF fund receipts, Gross NPF, and mudharabah income can contribute 22.56% of the GWM variable, and other variables outside the regression model can contribute 77.44%.

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

According to table 9, the test results prove that the probability value of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is 0.1137, which is said to be greater than 0.05. Apart from that, the test results reveal a negative trend with a coefficient of determination of -0.000475 and a t-statistic of -1.594862. So, receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has a negative impact on the Statutory Reserve (GWM). So the researcher's H1 hypothesis is that receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds affects GWM. Previous research by (Qonita & Ermawati, 2020) is in line with the findings of this research. Previous research shows that receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can increase total bank deposits, which has an impact on GWM. If total bank deposits increase, the GWM will also increase.

Effect of Gross NPF on Minimum Statutory Reserves (GWM)

The results of this test value prove a negative trend with a coefficient of 0.231043 and a t-statistic of 0.203126, as well as a probability value of NPF Gross of 0.8394, which can be said to be higher than 0.05. So, NPF Gross does not affect the Minimum Statutory Reserve. (GWM). The researcher's hypothesis H2: The influence of Gross NPF on GWM is rejected.

Previous research by Nurul Hidayatul M et al. (2023). The research results show that Gross NPF receipts can increase total bank deposits and increase GWM. However, receipt of current account deposits can also affect a bank's ROE, which is an indicator of a bank's financial performance that shows the company's performance in capital management.

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM)

Based on table 9, the test results show that mudharabah income has an impact on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWM), with a probability value of 0.1991, which is higher than 0.05, and a coefficient value of 0.000131 and a t-statistic value of 1.292085. So hypothesis H3, the researcher's hypothesis, is that mudharabah income has an impact on GWM.

The research results prove that mudharabah income can increase total bank deposits, increase GWM, and strengthen the bank's position in the market. This can help reduce profit risk.

Firm size moderates the influence of ZISWAF Fund Receipts on GWM

Table 9 shows the test results which show a positive direction with a coefficient of 2.46E-05 and a t-statistic value of 1.601459. The probability value of interaction between receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is 0.1122, concluded to be higher towards 0.05. Shows that profitability can weaken the influence between ZISWAF fund receipts and GWM. Therefore, hypothesis H4—company size moderates the effect of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on GWM—is accepted.

Previous research by (Rusmini & Aji, 2019) is in line with research findings. The research results prove that company size is a factor that can influence the influence of receiving zakat, infaq, alms, waqf (ZISWAF) funds on the Minimum Statutory Reserve (GWP) or Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Although GWP and GDP are not directly correlated with GWM, GWP and GDP are also not directly correlated with GWM.

Firm size moderates the influence of NPF Gross on GWM

The test results prove a negative trend with a coefficient of -0.036261 and a t-statistic of -0.505640, and the probability value of the interaction between NPF Gross and company size is 0.6141, which is greater than 0.05. The results show that profitability cannot increase the impact between Wadiah demand deposits and GWM. The hypothesis proposed by researchers, H5, is that company size moderates the influence between wadiah demand deposits and GWM.

Previous research by (Sugita et al., 2020) is in line with research findings. The research results show that the influence of company size on Gross NPF is very complex and depends on many factors. Higher companies typically have more customers, more marketing capabilities, efficiency, performance, management policies, suitability, funding structure, equity, and larger business size. However, they may also have higher expenses and more operating costs, which can reduce profits.

Firm size moderates the influence of Mudharabah Income on GWM

Table 9 shows the test results which show that the probability value of the interaction between mudharabah income and company size is 0.2008, which has a higher meaning. Against 0.05, the results of this test show a negative trend with a coefficient of -6.94E-06 and a t-statistic value -1.287100. The results show that profitability can weaken the influence between mudharabah income and reserve requirements. Therefore, the researcher's hypothesis, H6: Company size moderates the effect of mudharabah income on GWM, is accepted.

Previous research by (Navita, 2021) is in line with the findings of this study. The research results show that company size influences murabahah income as a moderator. Company size can influence murabahah revenues in various ways, including suitability, management policies, performance, efficiency, and marketing capabilities.

The Effect of Simultaneous Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Gross NPF, and Mudharabah Income on GWM

Because the significance value of 0.000019 is less than 0.05, it can be said that the variables ZISWAF fund receipts, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income have a relevant influence on GWM, as shown in the calculations in table 10. The results show that ZISWAF fund receipts, Gross NPF, and Mudharabah Income affect GWM simultaneously. Therefore, the researcher's hypothesis is H7: acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, Gross NPF, and Mudharabah Income is accepted.

The value for the coefficient of determination is 0.225600. The calculation of this figure shows that the three independent variables contribute 22.56%, with other factors

influencing 77.44% of the remainder. Therefore, additional independent variables can be used for further research.

CONCLUSION

The results of the T (partial) test show that ZISWAF fund receipts and mudharabah income have a relevant influence on the GWM. In other words, the more revenue and income from mudharabah and ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds generated, the higher the GWM. Gross NPPF has an irrelevant influence on GWM; in other words, if wadiah demand deposits are high, GWM will also increase, although not significantly.

For the F test (simultaneous), however, it was found that the variables ZISWAF fund receipts, Gross NPF, and mudharabah income influenced the GWM simultaneously. This shows that when these three variables are combined and analyzed, there is a less significant impact on the reserve requirement. This concludes that there is a correlation between the combination of these variables and the level of financing in Islamic banking. All independent variables—ZISWAF fund receipts, wadiah giro savings, and murabahah income—were only able to explain variations in GWM of 22.56% in the R² coefficient of determination test. These results show that this independent variable does not have a strong correlation or is unable to explain variations in GWM. This indicates that changes in the independent variables are likely to be insignificant.

This study cannot show significant trends for each variable because it only collects quarterly data from 2018 to 2023. In addition, it only uses five variables: ZISWAF fund receipts, total NPF, mudharabah income, GWM, and Firm size.

In further evidence, it is hoped to examine more independent variables to find out additional factors that influence the GWM and Islamic finance in Indonesia. In addition, it is recommended that the research object include other sharia share companies listed on the IDX.

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